

ISic0706

I.Sicily inscription 0706

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tom Gavin,Estella Kessler,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. d(is) m(anibus) s(acrum)

2. L(ucio) Arrio

3. Herme

4. vixit

5. mens(es) V

6. dies XXV

7. f(ecit) b(ene) m(erenti)

8. Chari

9. to ver

10. nae suo

Apparatus

Text from Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Sacred to the shades of the underworld. To Lucius Arrius Herma; he lived 5 months, 25 days. Charito made (this) for his well-deserving family slave.

Translation (de)

Den Seelen der Unterwelt gewidmet. Für Lucius Arrius Herma; er lebte für 5

Monate, 25 Tage. Charito hat (dies) gemacht für seinen verdienstvollen Sklaven.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175768

EDR 081511

EDCS 6100271

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1989.0341i

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 58

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0706. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4338921>